

Some Tidbits or Loose Ends about the Military by Brian Paul Kaess

Some of my friends were *apostates* when it came to patriotism, for they tinkered with the idea of joining the military, but shunned the idea once they realized the commitment it involved. 'Many are called but few are chosen!' as in the 'Parable of the Wedding Feast.' (Matthew 22:14). For some will claim that even Athens was ruined by its wars, but those must be rejected and cast aside. For indeed, I was drawn to the military 'like a moth to the flame.'

Sometime, during my Marine service, my Bible teacher Theresa Sohn, from the Chicago area, sent me a care package, filled with delicious sausages, that I promptly consumed. This was a wonderful and practical gift for a service person. It made Theresa, who is a bit *angelic* anyway, seem like an iteration of Florence Nightingale! I had a lot of penpals when I was in Cuba. I also wrote to Marys Desaulniers in Canada, Ya-Lan in Boston, and my friends and family back home. There was also an Army Reserve chick I met in a hotel in Albany, NY. Too many! But at least it kept me busy.

It struck me that people who serve in the military can be very *stoical*, and when they come home, they can become very *hedonistic*. And then there's the crowd who says, 'I could've, I would've, I should've, but never actually served in the military, so therefore, they don't have the type of commitment I had in that regard. Because it is not only the dudes with ten badges and ten rockers on their uniforms who have commitment or a sense of patriotism.

And then there was a time of 'high hopes,' when I was accepted to New Mexico Military Institute, and some even urged me to apply to West Point, but, in the end, I merely enlisted, being a person of *scant* funds. For if you call me low, then surely I must feel like *Cesar* who refused a crown.

And we can imagine back in 1989, when members of the *Politiburo* in Soviet Russia were discussing the Berlin Wall, and they said anxiously among themselves, 'how can we call ourselves a democratic society, if we need a barrier to contain our own people?' So, it was Gorbachev, not just Ronald Reagan or the Pope, who helped transition the Soviet Union from Marxism-Leninism to Social Democracy.

And so it should be that King Arthur, not merely Charlemagne, should be dubbed the 'Father of Europe,' since the former provided moral and spiritual guidance to Western Europe centuries before the Carolingian Dynasty, and as such, Charlemagne was simply the 'Landlord of Europe' or its caretaker, although his reign marked a revival of learning. For did not Charlemagne 'set the stage' for the feudal period, when many were tied to the land as peasants, and the church lorded it over many as a property owner. Across the sea, in a previous time, King Arthur's cavalry ranged the whole of southern Britain in their attempt to sweep the Anglo-Saxons from the isle, and represented a reassertion of Celtic pride in Sub-Roman Britian. However, maybe one can consider King Arthur and Charlemagne as being 'cut from the same cloth' since they were both considered one of the *Nine Worthies*, but perhaps King Arthur was the worthiest of them all!

By the 4th century, Roman decline had brought about an Anglo-Saxon invasion, and this caused the native Celtic and Romano-British forces to fuse together and resist. Their former rivalry was set aside in the face of a common enemy. Latinization and Christianity had been strongest in the Southeast. By 407 CE, with Rome in full retreat,

Britain south of Hadrian's Wall had become virtually independent. The Era of Sub-Roman Britain had begun. The Anglo-Saxons were arriving day-and-night by long boat from their cradle in northern Germany and something needed to be done.

In *extant* writings, it is mentioned that a 'supreme leader' or *dux bellorum* or simply 'dux' was elected to lead the charge. They checked the Irish from the west and the Picts from Caledonia, and halted the Saxons. This person, in Gildas' writings, and always of doubtful historicity, was believed to be the germ of the legend of King Arthur. Undoubtedly of Celtic origin, this person was also said to have Sarmatian ancestry as well. That a 'warlord' on the verge of the 5th-6th centuries did exist and help 'unite the tribes' and resist the invaders does have growing historical and archeological support. This was likely King Arthur.

One tribe, the *lazygae*, from the Sarmatians¹ of central Asia, had encountered Romans in battle, and, being captured, 5,500 of them were settled in Britain. They were often hired as fearsome armoured cavalry and mercenaries elsewhere. They certainly had their women and children with them, and many of these were likely Celts. In Nennius' *History*, three Sarmatian settlements or sites were later identified with three of the twelve sites of victories achieved by Arthur. Of these Sarmatians was a Roman named Artorius Castus and it is believed that the name Arthur may have been derived from this very Artorius, and that Arthur may have even been his descendant.

So, from these Sarmatian *cataphracts* or heavy cavalry and mercenaries, some scholars believe exists the background of the Arthurian legend. Note Arthur's warriors are mentioned as 'knights,' or cavalry. *Per* Geoffrey of Monmouth, every hero had to be a knight. The Sarmatians were known to be heavy lancers as well. These Sarmatian *cataphracts* were actually the 1st knights of European history and the founders of European Chivalry as well. The "knights" of Arthur probably consisted of Latinized and Celtized descendants of the Sarmatian mercenaries, and of Celtic cavalymen who fought in the Sarmatian way. The standard of the Dragon used by Arthur's army was also a Saka/Sarmatian symbol, and found among many ancient peoples. The last name Pendragon of Uther (Arthur's father from whom he inherited it) is rather Romano-Sarmatian as well. It means 'the son of the dragon' or 'he who fights under the banner of the dragon.'

Moreover, the *Epic Cycles* of Arthur and others were based on the lives of heroes of the fifth century CE, the exact period of the high dispersion of Sarmatian and Hunno-Sarmatian tribes in Central and West Europe. In one of these epics, the hero is mentioned as being 'armed in the ways of the Pannonians' (i.e. with two swords). It is known also that the Sarmatians used two swords. Indeed, archaeologists are discovering in the Sarmatian tombs gold plates almost always in pairs, which come from sword-sheaths. This evidence confirms that the typical Sarmatian warrior was armed with two swords. Parsifal and Sir Balin are both described as bearing two swords. After Balin's death, one of his swords is nailed to a marble or a rock by Merlin.

¹ See 'King Arthur', Arthurian Legend and the Sarmatians by Periklis Deliegiannis at academia.edu at

https://www.academia.edu/20226024/KING_ARTHUR_ARTHURIAN_LEGEND_AND_THE_SARMATIANS

Arthur's legend mentions the existence of two "magical swords". The first one was the sword of Uther, Arthur's father, which was nailed to a rock. Let it be noted that the medieval references of swords that are nailed to earth or to a rock are directly related to the Sarmatian religion. The second "magic sword" of the legend is the well-known *excalibur*, which Arthur received from the "Lady of the Lake."

The episode of *excalibur* is almost identical to the reports of 'magic swords' in the saga of Batradz, a hero of the Ossetians of the Caucasus, and also in the episode of Krabat's death which is included in a popular story of the modern Sorbs of eastern Germany. The modern Ossetes (Ossetians) are considered to be the last surviving Sarmatians, being descendants of an Alanic group which found refuge in the Caucasus. Also, modern ethnologists and linguists consider very probable that the Serbs/Sorbs and the Chrovates (Croats) were originally Sarmatian tribes.

Finally, according to Geoffrey, Arthur halted the Anglo-Saxon invasion. Nennius mentions that he did it by fighting twelve victorious battles against them. Archaeology confirms the repulse of the barbarians who did not conquer any new Briton territories for more than fifty years. The battles that Arthur gave are often located by scholars in sites covering almost the entire Great Britain. This would have only been possible for Arthur's cavalry who could have swept such a range.

So, while Charlemagne united much of Western Europe under the Carolingian Empire, King Arthur is a metaphorical "Father of Europe," - since he's the spiritual father of European ideals of knighthood, justice, and mythic unity. The *Grail Quest* elevates King Arthur from mere monarch to moral *exemplar* or compass. It was a *crucible* for Arthurian ideals and what was 'best in men.'